

APPENDIX B – EVALUATION RESULTS OF ELIGIBLE ORGANS AND ENTITIES FOR THE DRMI

Names of the Institutions	Criteria Scores									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Total
Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Federal University of Ouro Preto (UFOP)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Federal University of Ceará (UFC)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Federal University of Cariri (UFCA)	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	8
Federal University of Latin American Integration (UNILA)	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul (UFMS)	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	8
Federal University of Alagoas (UFAL)	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
Federal University of Amazonas (UFAM)	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
Federal University of Piauí (UFPI)	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	7
Federal University of the South and Southeast of Pará (UNIFESSPA)	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	7
Federal University of Alfenas (UNIFAL-MG)	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	7
Federal University of the Delta of Parnaíba (UFDPa)	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	7
Federal University of Roraima (UFRR)	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	7
Federal University of Sergipe (UFS)	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	7
Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ)	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	6
Federal University of São Carlos (UFSCAR)	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	6
Federal University of Maranhão (UFMA)	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	6
Federal University of the State of Rio de Janeiro (UNIRIO)	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	6

National Superintendence of Complementary Pension (PREVIC)	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	6
Federal Institute of Amapá (IFAP)	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	6
Federal Rural University of the State of Rio de Janeiro (UFRRJ)	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	6
Federal Institute of Piauí (IFPI)	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	5
Federal Institute of Pernambuco (IFPE)	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	5
Federal University of the Jequitinhonha and Mucuri Valleys (UFVJM)	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	5
Federal Rural University of the Semi-Arid (UFERSA)	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	4
Superintendence for the Development of the Midwest (SUDECO)	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	4
University of Brasília (UNB)	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	4
Federal Institute of Alagoas (IFAL)	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	4
National Agency for Land Transport (ANTT)	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	3
Federal University of Grande Dourados (UFGD)	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	3
Superintendence for the Development of the Amazon (SUDAM)	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	3
Federal Institute of Sergipe (IFS)	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	3
Federal University of Southern Bahia (UFSB)	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	3
Rui Barbosa House Foundation (FCRB)	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	3
Fluminense Federal University (UFF)	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1